

Assessing How Search Engines Affect Democratic Values: An Analysis from the Perspective of Information Ethics

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1. The influence of search engines

Search engines serve as critical information intermediaries, acting as mediators between content producers and users by collecting, selecting, weighting, and providing access to information. While they help navigate the vast amount of available information, they also shape the content that users can access. Consequently, the selection criteria used by search engines significantly influence what content is visible to the public and the knowledge structures through which it is understood. Therefore, it is essential to examine how the information selection practices of search engines affect democratic values.

2. How can the practices of search engines be ethically evaluated?

To analyze and assess the effects of digital technologies on democratic values, information scientist Helen Nissenbaum developed the framework of *Contextual Integrity*. Nissenbaum argues that technical systems in the digital age are often developed and implemented so quickly that there is little opportunity for societal negotiation regarding their alignment with social values and norms. Therefore, her framework suggests that we ethically evaluate new digital technologies by comparing them to established practices that have undergone social negotiation over time (Nissenbaum 2010, p. 107).

For search engines, public libraries serve as a relevant, longstanding context for this comparison: research indicates that library practices, especially in studies related to privacy, can be seen as precursors or parallels to online searches (Zimmer 2008, Nissenbaum 2010). Despite differences in user numbers, goals, and content formats, both libraries and search engines serve a similar function for information seekers: they facilitate the search for and discovery of content that meets the individual user's information needs. This parallel is illustrated by the reference queries made to librarians at the New York Public Library (NYPL) from the 1940s to the 1980s, ranging from "What was Napoleon's horse called?" to "What wig makers are there in Miami?" – demonstrating that questions we would now enter into search engines were once posed in public libraries.

Using the framework of *Contextual Integrity*, this paper assesses the impact of search engines on democratic values by analyzing whether selection rules of search engines threaten norms and values that have been established in the context of public libraries. Thus, a novel approach to the ethical assessment of search engine practices is presented: In public and academic discourse, the emphasis has so far mainly been on terms like "filter bubbles" and "echo chambers," focusing on how the selection practices of search engines impact the value of content diversity. This study broadens the perspective by demonstrating that search engines also influence a much wider array of societal values.

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3. Values in the context of information search in search engines and libraries

As a first step, this paper identifies the values relevant to information searching in both search engines and libraries. By examining the legal framework for information intermediaries in Germany, as well as the codes of ethics and declarations from professional associations related to search engines and libraries, eleven key values are identified: freedom of opinion and information, protection of children and minors, content diversity, privacy, transparency, protection of intellectual property, freedom from censorship, equality and non-discrimination, neutrality, reliability of sources, and sender transparency.

4. Do the practices of libraries and search engines promote or endanger societal values?

Search engines promote some of these values while simultaneously endangering others; similarly, libraries endanger some of these values while promoting others. For instance, search engines like *Google* and *Bing* threaten the value of equality and non-discrimination by reproducing discriminatory stereotypes. When users enter the search terms "Muslim women are," *Google* suggests phrases such as "Muslim women are dangerous," thereby reproducing anti-Muslim prejudices. In the German language version of *Google* image search, search result compilations also reproduce racist and sexist stereotypes. For example, the query "unprofessional hairstyles" (in German) primarily displays images of Black women, while the query "professional hairstyles" (in German) mostly shows pictures of *white* men and women. Libraries, too, reproduce sexist stereotypes by categorizing and presenting content according to gender. For example, some libraries label subject shelves with terms like "Women / Love", which solidifies outdated gender associations that suggest topics such as love are particularly relevant for women but of little interest to men (Leyrer 2025).

5. Suggestions for adjusting search engines and libraries

Both search engines and libraries pose risks to certain democratic values. To address this from an ethical standpoint, the selection practices of these intermediaries need to be redesigned to better promote democratic values. This paper offers several suggestions for implementing these changes. For instance, to uphold the values of equality and non-discrimination, search engines should develop a comprehensive strategy to systematically prevent their search suggestions and results from reproducing racist, sexist, and anti-Muslim stereotypes. The US-American social scientist Safiya Umoja Noble demands that search engine operators find a "permanent 'technical fix'" to prevent racist representations in search engines (Noble 2018, p. 155). To ensure that adjustments to selection rules effectively prevent discriminatory search suggestions and result lists, search engine operators should also appoint individuals to regularly and systematically check all language versions for discriminatory search results.

Libraries can promote equality and non-discrimination by avoiding gender-specific media presentation and recommendations. This means refraining from labeling topic shelves, interest groups, or recommendation lists in ways that target a particular gender. It is essential for library staff to understand the implications of gender-differentiated media practices. This can be achieved by incorporating this topic into library training programs, emphasizing it in continuing education, and including it in relevant specialist publications (Leyrer 2025).

6. Conclusion and Outlook

Information intermediaries like search engines and libraries are indispensable: they help us find the information that is relevant to us amidst the vast amount of available content. Therefore, it is crucial to design and regulate these intermediaries in ways that more effectively promote societal values. This

paper demonstrates how information intermediaries can be ethically assessed, resulting in specific recommendations for action to enhance their positive impact on society.

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